

Assessing the AhR-mediated activity of Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAHs) and their Methylated Derivatives using AhR-CALUX Bioassay

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1 Introduction

Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) are a group of organic compounds containing two or more fused aromatic rings. These environmental pollutants are ubiquitous and originate from the incomplete combustion of organic matter and/or mobilization by micro-organisms. Due to their hydrophobic nature, they tend to accumulate in sediments and soils, as well as in the tissues of living organisms, including humans (Goldman et al., 2001; Li et al., 2010). Meanwhile, PAHs in water are frequently detected as well (Li et al., 2010). PAHs are known to be harmful to human health and the environment, with some of them being carcinogenic and mutagenic (Goldman et al., 2001). To assess the potential toxicity of PAHs, 16 EPA PAHs are commonly monitored using instrumental analytical methods such as gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS). While it is a highly sensitive method, it has some limitations when it comes to assessing the bio-reactivity of PAHs and their mixtures. This is because PAHs are often present in complex mixtures, and the toxicity of these mixtures is difficult to predict based on the individual components alone (Andersson and Achten, 2015). In addition, derivative forms of PAHs, such as methylated PAHs (Me-PAHs), are also of growing concern since they are frequently detected in the environment and have been shown to be more toxic than their parent compounds (Larsson et al., 2018, 2014).

To address these challenges, the Chemically Activated Luciferase gene eXpression (CALUX) bioassay was developed to screen for activation of the aryl hydrocarbon receptor (AhR) signaling pathway, which is a well-known receptor for polycyclic aromatic compounds (He et al., 2011; Pieterse et al., 2013). This bioassay consists of recombinant cell lines that have been stably transfected with AhR-responsive luciferase reporter genes (Murk et al., 1996). Upon exposure to AhR agonists, the activation of AhR leads to the production of luciferase, which is proportional to the amount and potency of the ligands that are present in the sample to which the cells are exposed (Murk et al., 1996).

Although interactions between PAHs and AhR have been investigated previously using the CALUX cell line H4IIE cells (Larsson et al., 2014; Pieterse et al., 2013), few studies have assessed the relative potencies (REP) of Me-PAHs (see however Boonen et al., 2020). The aim of this study is to optimize the CALUX assay based on H1L7.5c1 cell lines (He et al., 2011) using benzo[a]pyrene (BaP) as a reference ligand and to assess the AhR-induced activity of sixteen EPA priority PAHs and five Me-PAHs individually and in the mixture. A growing body of experimental evidence indicates that the *in vitro* activities of these mixtures could be predicted from the overall response of their components using the concept of the concentration addition (CA) model and/or the independent mode of action (IA). Both of these models assume an additive effect, i.e. the chemicals in the mixture act together but do not interact with each other. This is the hypothesis we tested in this study with mixtures of 2-5 constituents including PAHs and Me-PAHs.

2 Materials and Methods

The PAHs, including naphthalene (Nap), acenaphthylene (Acy), acenaphthene (Ace), fluorene (Flu), phenanthrene (Phe), anthracene (Ant), fluoranthene (Fla), pyrene (Pyr), chrysene (Chr), benzo[a]anthracene (BaA), benzo[b]fluoranthene (BbF), benzo[k]fluoranthene (BkF), benzo[a]pyrene (BaP), dibenzo[a,h]anthracene (DahA), benzo[ghi]perylene (BghiP), and indeno[1,2,3-cd]pyrene (IcdP), as well as methylated PAHs, including 2-methylnaphthalene (2-MNaP), 5-methylchrysene (5-MChr), 1,3-dimethylnaphthalene (1,3-DMNap), 9,10-dimethylantracene (9,10-DMAnt), 7-methylbenzo[a]pyrene (7-MBap), were all purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Germany). The working solutions were diluted in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO, $\geq 99.7\%$, Sigma-Aldrich, Germany).

The cell cultural reagents were all purchased from Gibco by Life Technologies (the United Kingdom). The working alpha-Minimum Essential Medium (α -MEM) was supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS) and 1% penicillin-streptomycin (pen-strep). The working Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium (DMEM, without phenol red) was supplemented with 5% charcoal-stripped FBS, 2% l-glutamine (200 mM), 1% sodium pyruvate (100 mM, sterile-filtered), and 1% pen-strep. Trypsin (with and without phenol red, 10 \times , 0.5%) and phosphate buffered saline (PBS, 10 \times , pH 7.4) were diluted to 1 \times as working solution. Luciferin and lysis reagent were homemade.

With regard to the AhR-CALUX bioassay, H1L7.5c1 recombinant mouse hepatoma cell lines were used. In general, cells were cultured in working α -MEM and maintained in an incubator at 37 °C, 5% CO₂, and 80% humidity. The cells were seeded into 96-well plates at a density of 30,000 cells/well in 150 μ L of growth medium and allowed to incubate for 48 h prior to dosing. Next, 100 μ L of reclaimed media containing the desired concentration of the testing compounds were added to each well in triplicate, resulting in a final concentration of 1% (v/v) DMSO. After incubation for 2.75 h, the cells were washed with 100 μ L of PBS buffer and assessed for dead cells with a microscope before being lysed with 50 μ L of lysis buffer. Luciferase activity was measured using a luminometer (Tristar Reader, Berthold Technologies) with 50 μ L of luciferin added automatically. The light output was measured as relative light units (RLUs) after a counting time of 3 s. Medium blank and DMSO solvent blank were included on each plate as quality controls. The resulting RLUs were fitted to a four-parameter Hill equation according to Elskens et al. (2011).

3 Results

The reliability of the assay was first examined by analyzing the BaP calibration standards (n = 9) repeatedly. An example of BaP calibration curve is shown in Figure 1. The limit of detection (LOD), defined as 10% of maximum response, was found to be 0.4 ± 0.1 pg/well, while the limit of quantification (LOQ), defined as 20% of maximum response, was determined to be 2.8 ± 0.8 pg/well. A positive control (PC, 47 pg BaP/well) was measured in triplicate in each plate to monitor the quality of the calibration curve. The coefficient of variance (CV) of intra-laboratory repeatability was 15.5%, and CV of intra-laboratory reproducibility was 13.2%. The accuracy of the assay was expressed as percent error of measured PC, ranging from -11.5 to 11.6% with an average of 5.1%.

Figure 1: Example of BaP concentration-response curve.

The agonistic activities of sixteen EPA PAHs and five Me-PAHs were tested using PAH-CALUX. Among these chemicals, Ace, Flu, Nap, Phe, 1,3-DMNap, and 2-MNAP did not produce any response. It suggests that the absence of activation of the parent PAHs on the AhR may lead to the lack of response of their corresponding Me-PAHs on the same receptor. However, it should be noted that this conclusion does not apply to the entire PAC family, as 9,10-DMAnt was also identified as a non-AhR agonist, while Ant was reported as a weak AhR agonist in this study.

The relative potency (REP) is a measure of the potency of a chemical relative to a reference chemical, typically expressed as EC₅₀ value of a thoroughly characterized standard (BaP in this study) by that of a sample or pure compound. The results of REPs showed that BkF was the most potent PAC congener with a relative potency of 7.2, followed by DahA > BbF > IcdP > 5-MChr > 7-MBaP were all higher than BaP (Table 1). It suggests that these compounds have the potential to pose a greater risk to human health. It is interesting to note that some of the compounds with higher REP values, such as 7-MBaP and 5-MChr, are methylated forms of BaP, suggesting that the addition of a methyl group can increase the potency of these compounds.

It is important to note that the assessment of potency and efficacy solely based on REP values can be intricate because their evaluation can vary with target receptors or enzymes in different cell species. In addition, REP is only applicable if the dose-response curves for the test compounds and standard are parallel (i.e., with the same Hill coefficient) and possess the same efficacy (i.e., maximum achievable response). But these conditions are often either violated or cannot be demonstrated. Consequently, the inclusion of maximum response, Hill coefficients, and EC₅₀ in our results is also listed to have a better understanding of the characteristics of these compounds (Table 1).

Table 1: Dose-Response curve parameters for PAHs and their derivatives. All experiments were performed in 3 independent experiments with triplicate measurements of each tested concentration on one plate, and the data were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD).

Compounds	Max. RLU (%)	Hill coefficient	EC50 (pg/well)	REP50
5-Methylchrysene	97.7 \pm 3.3	1.0 \pm 0.4	14.8 \pm 1.2	2.4 \pm 0.4
7-Methylbenzo[a]pyrene	97.1 \pm 3.2	0.8 \pm 0.2	23.6 \pm 1.0	1.2
Acenaphthylene	70.0 \pm 4.4 **	1.3	(39.9 \pm 1.5) $\times 10^4$	< 0.0001
Anthracene	76.9 \pm 1.3 **	1.1 \pm 0.1	(153.6 \pm 30.5) $\times 10^2$	0.002
Benz[a]anthracene	94.6 \pm 1.3	0.8 \pm 0.1	49.6 \pm 4.7	0.6 \pm 0.1
Benzo[a]pyrene	96.5 \pm 0.2	0.9 \pm 0.2	28.2 \pm 7.2	1.00
Benzo[b]fluoranthene	98.2 \pm 2.9	0.7 \pm 0.1	10.8 \pm 3.7	3.3 \pm 0.3
Benzo[ghi]perylene	78.56 \pm 0.6 *	1.0 \pm 0.1	(2.9 \pm 0.2) $\times 10^3$	0.01
Benzo[k]fluoranthene	106.2 \pm 4.7	0.7 \pm 0.1	4.0 \pm 0.6	7.2 \pm 1.2
Chrysene	100.1 \pm 2.3	1.0 \pm 0.1	30.3 \pm 9.1	1.00 \pm 0.4
Dibenz[a,h]anthracene	101.2 \pm 1.2	0.6 \pm 0.1	7.1 \pm 0.7	4.0 \pm 0.4
Fluoranthene	34.0 \pm 2.7 **	2.4 \pm 0.6 **	(8.4 \pm 2.8) $\times 10^5$	< 0.0001
Indeno[1,2,3-cd]pyrene	97.8	0.9 \pm 0.1	11.2 \pm 2.1	2.6 \pm 0.5
Pyrene	11.2 \pm 1.4 **	1.4 \pm 1.2 **	n.a.	n.a.

n.a.: not available

*p<0.05, **p<0.01 (p-values are in reference to the comparison with BaP)

4 Discussion

According to our knowledge, this was the first study to test the AhR-activity of 7-MBaP, 1,3-DMNap, 2-MNap, and 9,10-DMAnt. By comparing the REP values, this study demonstrated that BkF, DahA, BbF, and IcdP were more potent AhR agonists than BaP, which is consistent with previous findings from Pieterse et al. (2013). However, the order of potency among the PAHs differed between both studies. In accordance with this study, Pieterse et al. (2013) also reported that Ace, Acy, Ant, Fla, Flu, Nap, and Phe were weak or non-agonists in their assay. Moreover, they reported REPs of 5-MChr and Chr to be 1.4 and 0.8, respectively, which were lower than those found in this study. However, the finding that methylated form is more potent than its parent remained the same. Differences in the detection of AhR agonist activity for some PAHs were also observed. For example, Amakura et al. (2016) found weak AhR agonist activity for Flu, which was not observed in our studies. These findings suggest that the choice of cell line and experimental parameters can impact the detection of AhR agonist activity for PACs. For the experiment with mixtures, in 95% of the cases, the observed pattern was a joint and independent effect of PAHs and Me-PAHs on the AhR. Overall, these results validate a risk assessment approach based on an additive effect model possibly modulated by intrinsic toxicity factors.

5 Conclusions

This study presents a rapid, reliable, sensitive, and accurate method for screening the activity of PACs. The agonist activity of sixteen PAHs and 5 methylated derivatives was determined with twelve of them showing strong agonistic activity. Future analysis of antagonistic activity will provide more insight and information about mixture effects.

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7 References

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